

Green Transportation and Economic Performance in Food Supply Chain: An Operational Perspective

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Abstract- This paper will explore economic performance of supply chain and green transportation in transportation from an operations and strategic fit perspective. Contrary to traditional economic performance of supply chain and green transportation in transportation which addresses the cost of sustainability, this paper will address the operational aspect of sustainability in supply chain and green transportation in transportation which can be aligned with economic performance through supply chain strategic fit which accounts for the inherent uncertainty and demand-response nature of supply goods. Sustainability as an operation rather than a cost will be aligned with economic performance through supply chain strategic fit which addresses product requirements through an efficiency-responsiveness frontier.

Keywords: "Green Transportation"; "Food Supply Chain", "Strategic Fit"; "Operational Efficiency"; "Sustainable Logistics".

I. INTRODUCTION

There is greater interest in managing the food supply chain at a global level to make it not only more efficient but also environmentally sustainable (Shakuri & Barzinpour, 2024). This interest is especially pertinent given that climate change and environmental and resource sustainability are issues of global concern (Su et al., 2023). Transportation plays a substantial role in the emissions of greenhouse gases and pollution in the food supply chain (Ding et al., 2025). "The reliance on fossil fuels for transportation is often the cheapest alternative in the short term but carries considerable environmental and regulatory risks in the long term (Ding et al., 2025).

Thereafter, the concept of green transportation has emerged as a strategic mechanism to address these effects (Gökoğlan et al., 2024). Green transportation involves using clean vehicles, alternative fuels, route optimization, consolidation, and inter-modal transportation to reduce the carbon footprint of transporting food from farmers to consumers (Helo & Ala-Harja, 2018).

These innovative measures to improve food transportation systems are closely related to

Sustainable Development Goals 12 and 13 of the United Nations (Chan-drasiri et al., 2024). There are several obstacles to the adoption of green transportation for perishable goods transportation due to the complexity of green transportation operations (Yan et al., 2022). On the other hand, the costs of green transportation of food should be balanced with the financial benefits from environmental regulations (Sivasankari & Ramesh, 2025).

On the other hand, realizing these financial rewards is complicated by the cost-environmental benefit trade-off (Nkesah, 2023). Nonetheless, theoretical frameworks and empirical research underscore the gains of green logistics in both environmental and financial terms (Chatzoudes et al., 2024).

In practice, gaining visibility into the connectivity and interplay between green transportation and key performance measures in the food supply chain—such as total costs, delivery quality, and inventory turnover—could become a critical focus for analysis and exploration amid increasingly challenging regulatory and consumer requirements (Bottani et al., 2022). The discussion on integrating green transportation into the food supply chain extends beyond mere environmental concerns ("greenness") and can also be framed as an operations

management perspective, which could be further argued to be the most appropriate lens for examining such integration (Zhang & Shang, 2025).

The food chain is complex due to the perishable nature of the products, the need for maintaining high-quality delivery, the cooling requirement during transportation, and high coordination costs across and between firms and their customers (Popa et al., 2025)." As mentioned above, in the given setting, strategic and "macro" studies overlook the operational decisions that operating managers have to make on a routine basis and the trade-offs that they face (Ataburo et al., 2024). This study employs an "operational" approach to pay attention to more "micro"-level decisions that are critical to environmental and cost performance (Jeong & Lee, 2022). A perspective-based approach is expected to offer greater congruence with sustainability goals and organizational performance indicators (Shakuri & Barzinpour, 2024). Corporate sustainability reports track not only carbon footprints but also on-time delivery rates, total logistics costs, asset utilization, and inventory turnover, which are the responsibilities of operational personnel (Dovbischuk, 2021; Reshetnikova, 2021). Anchoring green transportation at the operations perspective means that the solutions we offer would not only be environmentally sound and economically viable but also have the potential to be integrated within existing logistics constraints (Younus et al., 2023).

The importance of green transport in food supply chains, from the academic and practitioner points of view, is (Zhang & Shang, 2025): From the academic point of view, it is a new research field that brings together the topics of sustainability science, operations management, and environmental economics, and it has great potential to study the environmental-cost trade-offs (Argoubi & Mili, 2026). It includes the optimization models for logistics with sustainability constraints and the sustainable supply chain management theory (Wu et al., 2023). From the practitioner point of view, the importance of the subject is rising within the context of growing environmental regulations, growing fuel costs, growing environmental awareness of the customers, and carbon neutral commitment of the

enterprises, which makes food supply chains reconsider their transport strategies without jeopardizing the service quality and cost-effectiveness (Talib & Zulfakar, 2023).

Hence, this research—which investigates the effects of green transportation practices on operational performance—addresses an essential gap in the existing literature, holding high relevance for logistics practitioners, policymakers, and supply chain managers pursuing environmental sustainability (Chatzoudes et al., 2024).

The scope of this paper is to examine the effect of green transportation on the economic performance of food supply chain at the operational level. It will contribute to integrating the theories covered under the umbrella of sustainable logistics with their practical implementation to analyze the trade-offs, coordination and the practices of implementation of a feasible food supply chain from an environmental perspective. The paper begins with a background and justification of the operations management perspective and then explores the relationships between the implementation of green transportation practices in food supply chain and its influence on different aspects of relevant financial performance. Then it highlights the operational challenges and enablers and concludes with implications and future research directions.

II. DEVELOPMENT OF THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

Based on the preceding arguments, SSCM offers a general structure for integrating environmental issues into basic supply chain functions and positions green transportation as a key driver of sustainability (Zhang & Shang, 2025). The resource-based view builds on this by theorizing green logistics capabilities—such as eco-friendly transportation modes and route management—as strategic and rare assets (Basana et al., 2022). Because these assets are valuable, unique, and difficult to imitate, they serve as a source of competitive advantage and lead to superior economic performance (Çek & Ercantan, 2023). Taking these together, the view is additive to the evolution from

seeing green transportation as a regulatory compliance cost to an operational capability, now being used as a means of enabling shared advancement of both sustainability and food supply chain profitability (Talib & Zulfakar, 2023). The most important events in the history of green transportation in the food supply chain are the transition in the early 2000's from cost-only to a triple bottom line supply chain, the integration of carbon footprint as part of the supply chain planning in the early 2010's and in the last two years the move towards a new circular economy / zero-carbon supply chain (Asif et al., 2023). On the legislative side, the EU Green Deal and the tightening of emission standards have been two of the most important factors influencing the industry. Last but not least, the industry has moved from the identification of sustainability as the nemesis of the supply chain efficiency to its application as a source of innovation for the future supply chain economic performance (Chen, 2024).

The mainstream understanding of green transport in food supply chains revolves around "eco-efficiency," where sustainability is viewed as part of operational excellence (Gökoçlan et al., 2024). However, more recent ideas advocate systemic change, particularly emphasizing decarbonization as an unavoidable strategic imperative rather than merely a desirable efficiency goal (Abdelraheem et al., 2025). Examples include circular logistics systems, demand-responsive distribution systems, the adoption of zero-emission technologies in cold chain logistics, and greater emphasis on transparency, collaboration, and regulatory foresight (Rastegardebidi & Su, 2025). Literature and practice clearly indicate that we must consider not only how food is transported but also when, where, and whether it needs to be transported at all; to achieve sustainability, we must shift from system optimization to systems thinking (Corigliano et al., 2025).

The rationality of the operational perspective can be understood from the fact that it provides a direct link between green transportation and decisions that affect cost efficiency and service performance (Popa et al., 2025). Being time- and quality-sensitive and

involving the use of a substantial amount of resources, the feasibility of green transportation in food logistics should be understood in the context of operational-level decisions (Ala-Harja & Helo, 2014). The operational perspective makes a direct connection between decisions that affect cost efficiency and service performance and those that affect green transportation; therefore, the research is feasible and does not suffer from the implementation gap that normally exists with top-down approaches to sustainability (Trigos & Osorio, 2025). In addition, the operational perspective helps identify potential win-win situations in green transportation that simultaneously improve productivity and environmental impact and hence makes the case for sustainability from a rational and credible perspective (Younus et al., 2023).

Integration of theory, practice, and context is needed to advance the discussion on green transportation in food supply chains (Zhang & Shang, 2025). On the theory side, it is sustainable operations management and resource-based theories that provide the logic for the potential of green logistics to create value (Mastos & Gotzamani, 2022). On the practice side, it is the practicalities of cold chain management, truck replacement cycles, and last-mile options that determine what can and cannot be done (Lun et al., 2014). On the context side, it is the context that determines how these two are combined based on, for example, regional variations in policy, technology, markets, and consumer preferences (Liu et al., 2025). The strength of the operational perspective is that it can combine all three to provide context-dependent advice that is theoretically valid and practically relevant—so that not only are environmental benefits achieved, but they are also operationally feasible and economically viable (Sherif & Salonitis, 2025).

III. COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVES AND CRITICAL REFLECTION

A critical comparison of the available research in this field—both academic and practitioner-oriented—has revealed both agreement and disagreement regarding the green transportation concept and its applications in the food supply chain (Zhang &

Shang, 2025). The extant academic literature on green transportation in the food supply chain focuses on optimization models, life cycle assessments, carbon foot-print analyses, and the like (Maiyar & Thakkar, 2019).

The studies conducted to analyze the significance of food supply chain are hypo-thetical, assumption-based, and have not considered the real problems that must be solved in food supply chain (De et al., 2022). The perspective that will tackle the real problems is the operational perspective.

It recognizes that while industry often requires balancing trade-offs amid uncertainty, academia seeks comprehensive solutions to the entire problem (Bhattacharya & Ishizaka, 2025). By emphasizing "levers" such as dynamic routing, load balancing, and technology adoption strategies, it offers a more holistic perspective on both the quality and applicability of solutions.(Farahi, 2025)

An examination of the assumptions underlying the current discussion of green transportation in food supply chains reveals several assumptions that have been unquestionably built into the discussion(Rossi et al., 2020). 1. Technological substitution will generate significant environmental and economic benefits. This assumption neglects upstream emissions, grid decarbonization, and the applicability of electric trucks in temperature-controlled food transportation (Elangovan et al., 2021). 2. There is also an assumption of homogeneity in supply chain structures, in which the food logistics system is treated as a whole, disregarding the huge disparity between, for example, fresh produce and frozen food supply chains (Osman et al., 2023). 3. There is an assumption that eco-efficiency goes hand in hand with profitability, failing to account for situations where eco-efficient practices could lead to higher costs in the short- to medium-term, for which there is no return on investment, particularly for SMEs(Agrawal et al., 2023). 4. Lastly, the above conventional methods.

usually take it for granted that companies are willing and prepared to adopt green technology, without considering cultural resistance, conflicting interests,

and the absence of environmental–operational performance measurements (Huang et al., 2022). These assumptions need to be challenged to create more realistic, fair, and culturally friendly food logistics and supply chain strategies.

There are some very important contextual factors missing from green transportation in the food supply chain debate (Mogale et al., 2022). First, the social equity and labor context, such as the impact of fleet electrification on the training requirements, displacement, or working conditions of drivers, particularly in the cold chain (Taghi-khah et al., 2019). Second, the frequently overlooked distinction between urban and rural, or high- and low-income regions, including the infrastructure that may or may not be available to support green solutions that are viable in urban, well-resourced regions(Li et al., 2024). Fourth, the issue of power relations between different actors in the supply chain, where large retailers impose the rules on sustainability while passing the bill to smaller actors, is not considered but is also important in understanding who bears the burden of the transition (Karaosman et al., 2024). Lastly, behavioral and organizational factors, such as resistance to change, risk aversion, or coordination, are also not considered, yet they are critical in the success of the implementation of sustainable transportation strategies

IV. PRACTICAL AND STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS

The proposed operational perspective will have several practical implications for practitioners in the food supply chain (Rossi et al., 2020). First, it will help practitioners shift from viewing green transportation merely as a compliance cost to seeing it as a source of operational efficiencies and competitive advantage, thereby enabling them to leverage cost-GHG reduction synergies (Changalima et al., 2025). Second, it will help practitioners approach decision-making under real-world constraints in a more systematic and holistic manner, thereby enabling their green transportation efforts to be operationally feasible (Su et al., 2025). Third, it will help practitioners think in a more collaborative manner, thereby enabling them to align departmental goals

in green transportation with overall business performance metrics (Weng, 2025). Fourth, it will also help practitioners think in a more incremental and step-by-step manner about how to operationalize their green transportation efforts, thereby enabling them to do so without requiring significant investment (Kaledinova & Tran, 2025).

At the institutional level, compliance is no longer voluntary, but a condition of market access and public subsidy. Furthermore, there is growing recognition that policy must be feasible, and that any policy that did not account for implementation details such as the existing fleet of vehicles, refrigeration requirements, or logistics of small farmers may impose economic hardship or lead to non-compliance. By focusing on pragmatic policymaking that is informed by implementation, policymakers can make more empirically informed decisions that better balance environmental policy with economic reality. This makes it possible to develop more targeted incentives (e.g., subsidies for electric refrigerated vans or route optimization software) that better align with institutional priorities and capacity for implementation, speeding the transition to sustainable food logistics.

V. FUTURE OUTLOOK AND RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Finally, the predicted vision of green transportation in FSC is the merging of sustainability with logistics services (Barbieri et al., 2024). Predicted current and future green transportation in FSC trends include autonomous electric vehicles, AI dynamic routes, blockchain emissions tracking, and hydrogen refrigerated transportation (Jahagirdar, 2025). The possibilities of these trends are significant and far-reaching and go beyond just improvement. However, these possibilities can only be realized through research in several areas.

First, context-dependent operating models, which account for the differences in infrastructure, policy development, and SC configurations in developing countries with limited data and resources, should be developed (Gavalas, 2025). Second, more research should be done on the relationship between the

circular economy and transportation practices, such as reusable packaging and backhauling, to reduce waste and mileage (Mbago et al., 2025). Third, more attention should be devoted to behavioral and organizational issues, including change management, inter-tier cooperation, and incentive alignment, which are essential for successful adoption (Kudrenko & Hall, 2024). Fourth, longitudinal studies should be carried out to investigate the real cost trade-offs and ROI of green investments, in particular in SMEs (Bacchiocchi et al., 2024). Fifth, a set of integrated KPIs which embrace all three dimensions of sustainability, i.e., environmental, economic, and social, should be conceptualized to facilitate more informed decisions (Estébanez & Martín, 2025). By addressing these knowledge gaps, researchers and practitioners can co-create sustainable food logistics systems that remain sustainable over time.

Future directions and new opportunities in green transportation in food supply chains will still be driven by the same three drivers, that is, environmental concerns, technology advancements, and stakeholder requirement. The challenges in green transportation in food supply chains include: high initial costs and limited availability of zero-emission refrigerated trucks, inadequate charging/refueling infrastructure in rural or transboundary areas, technology challenges in refrigeration under alternative fuels, absence of unified regulations that causes confusion in complying with regional regulations, inadequate data to measure GHG reductions and cost savings at the operational level, and labor challenges in training drivers and technicians to manage new technologies.

However, these are just as critical. Advances in battery technology, renewable energy, and AI-enabled route-optimization platforms make for a far more intelligent, sustainable, and flexible transportation system. So too do green subsidies, tax breaks, and relief from low-emission zones. Equally, the demand of consumers and retailers for a more transparent, sustainable food chain provides market-driven pull. Collaborative models such as shared electric fleets and urban consolidation centers offer a scalable, low-emission and low-cost solution. By

acting early, food supply chain companies can make green transportation an enabler rather than an enforcer.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our exploration of green transportation through the lens of operations demonstrates the opportunity for green transportation to be a shining light of sustainability and a key driver of economic value in the food industry. Obviously, it is clear that green transportation is not just some "green" initiative at the periphery of the business model. It is at the core of the business model, in the operations of the business. There are a lot of obstacles to overcome in the food industry. There are a lot of infrastructure and organizational obstacles. However, the technology and policy and market drivers are opening up new opportunities for green transportation. Sustainability in operations is at the heart of our strategy. We do not have to succumb to the traditional trade-offs of sustainability and efficiency and profitability. The sustainability of the food industry will not be determined by our acts of heroism. It will be determined by our everyday choices in bringing food from farm to fork.

REFERENCES

1. Abdelraheem, A. A. E., Musa, A. M. H., Khogly, M. E. M., & Elboukhari, Y. (2025). Consolidating sustainability efforts: The role of effective supply chain management in balancing economic growth, environmental stewardship, and social responsibility. *Journal of Project Management*, 10(3), 533. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.jpm.2025.4.001>
2. Agrawal, R., Tommasi, L. D., Lyons, P., Zaroni, S., Papagiannis, G. K., Karakosta, C., Papapostolou, A., Durand, A., Martínez, L. B., Fragidis, G., Corbella, M., Sileni, L., Neusel, L., Repetto, M., Mariuzzo, I., Kakardakos, T., & Güemes, E. L. (2023). Challenges and opportunities for improving energy efficiency in SMEs: Learnings from seven European projects. *Energy Efficiency*, 16(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-023-10090-z>
3. Ala-Harja, H., & Helo, P. (2014). Green supply chain decisions – Case-based performance analysis from the food industry. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 69, 97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2014.05.015>
4. Argoubi, M., & Mili, K. (2026). Multi-objective optimization framework for sustainable olive oil supply chains: Integrating environmental compliance with economic performance. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2025.1711821>
5. Asif, M. S., Lau, H. C. W., Nakandala, D., & Hurriyet, H. (2023). Paving the way to net-zero: Identifying environmental sustainability factors for business model innovation through carbon disclosure project data. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1214490>
6. Ataburo, H., Ampong, G. E., & Essuman, D. (2024). Developing operational resilience to navigate transportation disruptions: The role and boundaries of efficiency priority. *Annals of Operations Research*, 340, 723. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-024-06092-4>
7. Bacchiocchi, A., Bellocchi, A., & Giombini, G. (2024). Green investment challenges in European firms: Internal vs. external resources. *Sustainability*, 16(2), 496. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020496>
8. Barbieri, F., Cannava, L., Colicchia, C., & Perotti, S. (2024). Modelling the environmental performance of logistics distribution processes: A business case in the agri-food supply chain. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 32(11), 51. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bij-07-2024-0634>
9. Basana, S. R., Siagian, H., Ubud, S., & Tarigan, Z. J. H. (2022). The effect of top management commitment on improving operational performance through green purchasing and green production. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 10(4), 1479. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2022.6.008>
10. Bhattacharya, A., & Ishizaka, A. (2025). Computational logistics in the food and drink industry: Advances in modelling and applications. *Annals of Operations Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-025-06887-z>

11. Bottani, E., Casella, G., Nobili, M., & Tebaldi, L. (2022). An analytic model for estimating the economic and environmental impact of food cold supply chain. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4771. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084771>
12. Chandrasiri, C., Kiridena, S., Dharmapriya, S., & Kulatunga, A. K. (2024). Adoption of multi-modal transportation for configuring sustainable agri-food supply chains in constrained environments. *Sustainability*, 16(17), 7601. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16177601>
13. Changalima, I. A., Rutatola, P. P., & Ntangeki, G. G. (2025). Trending research topics on carbon footprint and supply chains: A bibliometric analysis based on Scopus data (2019–2023). *Future Business Journal*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-025-00445-6>
14. Chatzoudes, D., Kadłubek, M., & Maditinios, D. (2024). Green logistics practices: The antecedents and effects for supply chain management in the modern era. *Equilibrium Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy*, 19(3), 991. <https://doi.org/10.24136/eq.2864>
15. Chen, R. (2024). Sustainable supply chain management as a strategic enterprise innovation. *Advances in Economics Management and Political Sciences*, 85(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/85/20240831>
16. Çek, K., & Ercantan, Ö. (2023). The relationship between environmental innovation, sustainable supply chain management, and financial performance: The moderating role of ESG. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 12(2), 176. <https://doi.org/10.33844/ijol.2023.60358>
17. Corigliano, O., Morrone, P., & Algieri, A. (2025). Navigating the challenges of sustainability in the food processing chain: Insights into energy interventions to reduce footprint. *Energies*, 18(2), 296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18020296>
18. De, A., Gorton, M., Hubbard, C., & Aditjandra, P. (2022). Optimization model for sustainable food supply chains: An application to Norwegian salmon. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 161, 102723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2022.102723>
19. Ding, Y., Zhang, L., Kuo, Y., & Zhang, L. (2025). Cold chain routing for product freshness and low carbon emissions: A target-oriented robust optimization approach. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 199, 104138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2025.104138>
20. Dovbischuk, I. (2021). Sustainable firm performance of logistics service providers along maritime supply chain. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 8040. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13148040>
21. Elangovan, R., Kanwhen, O., Dong, Z., Mohamed, A., & Rojas-Cessa, R. (2021). Comparative analysis of energy use and greenhouse gas emission of diesel and electric trucks for food distribution in NYC. *Frontiers in Big Data*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2021.693820>
22. Farahi, R. (2025). A comprehensive overview of load balancing methods in software-defined networks. *Discover Internet of Things*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43926-025-00098-5>
23. Gavalas, D. (2025). Supply chain resilience in the face of uncertainty: A study of wheat trade and supply chain optimization. *Acta Logistica*, 12(1), 103. <https://doi.org/10.22306/al.v12i1.593>
24. Gökoğlan, K., Elaldi, M., & Sevim, H. (2024). Green supply chain implications for food industry. *Pressacademia*. <https://doi.org/10.17261/pressacademia.2024.1881>
25. Helo, P., & Ala-Harja, H. (2018). Green logistics in food distribution – A case study. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 21(4), 464. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13675567.2017.1421623>
26. Huang, Y., Chen, A. P. S., Do, M., & Chung, J.-C. (2022). Assessing the barriers of green innovation implementation: Evidence from the Vietnamese manufacturing sector. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4662. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084662>
27. Jeong, S., & Lee, J. (2022). The impact of environmental management systems on energy efficiency. *Manufacturing & Service Operations*

- Management, 24(3), 1311.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/msom.2021.1057>
28. Kaledinova, E., & Tran, N. (2025). Interrelation of sustainability indicators and sustainable solutions in road freight transportation. *Business, Management and Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1010276>
29. Karaosman, H., Marshall, D., & Ward, I. (2024). For the many not the few: Introducing just transition for supply chain management. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijopm-07-2023-0587>
30. Kudrenko, I., & Hall, L. (2024). Adoption of reusable transit packaging in US industries. *Review of Managerial Science*, 19(9), 2633. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-024-00826-1>
31. Li, Y., Archetti, C., & Ljubić, I. (2024). Emerging optimization problems for distribution in same-day delivery. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2405.05620>
32. Liu, Y., Hou, J., & Cai, C. (2025). Optimization of cold chain logistics distribution routes considering time-dependent networks. *PLoS ONE*, 20(9). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0330535>
33. Lun, Y. H. V., Lai, K., Wong, C. W. Y., & Cheng, T. C. E. (2014). Greening propensity and performance implications for logistics service providers. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 74, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2014.10.002>
34. Maiyar, L. M., & Thakkar, J. J. (2019). Robust optimisation of sustainable food grain transportation with uncertain supply and intentional disruptions. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(18), 5651. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1656836>
35. Mastos, T., & Gotzamani, K. (2022). Sustainable supply chain management in the food industry: A conceptual model. *Foods*, 11(15), 2295. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11152295>
36. Mbago, M., Ntayi, J. M., Mkansi, M., Namagembe, S., Tukamuhabwa, B., & Mwelu, N. (2025). Implementing reverse logistics practices in the supply chain: A case study analysis of recycling firms. *Modern Supply Chain Research and Applications*, 7(2), 200. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mscra-01-2025-0003>
37. Mogale, D. G., Ghadge, A., Cheikhrouhou, N., & Tiwari, M. K. (2022). Designing a food supply chain for enhanced social sustainability in developing countries. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(10), 3184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2022.2078746>
38. Nkesah, S. K. (2023). Making road freight transport more sustainable: Insights from a systematic literature review. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 22, 100967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100967>
39. Osman, S. A., Xu, C., Akufu, M., & Paul, E. R. (2023). Perishable food supply chain management: Challenges and the way forward. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(7), 349. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2023.117025>
40. Popa, I., Stănescu, S. G., Duică, A., Molnár, E. I., & Duică, M. C. (2025). Cost optimisation of supply chains in the food industry: Cost function modelling. *Amfiteatru Economic*, 27(69), 293. <https://doi.org/10.24818/ea/2025/69/293>
41. Rastegardebidi, P., & Su, Z. (2025). Key drivers of green logistics: A systematic literature review and conceptual framework. *Sustainability*, 17(21), 9604. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17219604>
42. Reshetnikova, O. (2021). Promoting pro-ecological behavior with logistics operators in Poland and Ukraine. *Rocznik Ochrona Środowiska*, 23, 642. <https://doi.org/10.54740/ros.2021.045>
43. Rossi, T., Pozzi, R., Pirovano, G., Cigolini, R., & Pero, M. (2020). A new logistics model for increasing economic sustainability of perishable food supply chains through intermodal transportation. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 24(4), 346. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13675567.2020.1758047>
44. Shakuri, M., & Barzinpour, F. (2024). A risk-averse sustainable perishable food supply chain considering production and delivery times with real-world application. *PLoS ONE*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0308332>

45. Sherif, Z., & Salonitis, K. (2025). A systematic review of decision tools for process selection and performance improvement in manufacturing. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 141, 1113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-025-16806-y>
46. Su, I.-H., Wu, L., & Tan, K. H. (2023). The future of the food supply chain: A systematic literature review and research directions. *Journal of Digital Economy*, 2, 303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdec.2024.03.001>
47. Su, J., Lin, Q., & Chen, M. (2025). Optimizing carbon footprint in long-haul heavy-duty E-truck transportation. *Nature Communications*, 16(1), 9562. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-64792-2>
48. Taghikhah, F., Voinov, A., & Shukla, N. (2019). Extending the supply chain to address sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 229, 652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.051>
49. Talib, M. S. A., & Zulfakar, M. H. (2023). Sustainable halal food supply chain management in a small rentier halal market. *Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Re-search*, 42(3), 449. <https://doi.org/10.1108/agjsr-11-2022-0251>
50. Trigos, F., & Osorio, M. L. (2025). Integrating the triple bottom line into the vehicle routing problem. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2025.1528514>
51. Weng, L. (2025). Green logistics in 2025: Integrating sustainability, technology, and business strategy. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5168169>
52. Wu, Y., Wang, S., Zhen, L., & Laporte, G. (2023). Integrating operations research into green logistics: A review. *Frontiers of Engineering Management*, 10(3), 517. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42524-023-0265-1>
53. Yan, B., Liu, Y., & Fan, J. (2022). Two-echelon fresh product supply chain with different transportation modes. *Annals of Operations Research*, 349(2), 1379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-022-05092-6>
54. Younus, M., Purnomo, E. P., Husein, R., & Khairunnisa, T. (2023). Towards a greener future: Promoting green and sustainable development in transportation operation. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 440, 1004. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202344001004>
55. Zhang, Y., & Shang, J. (2025). Green technology investment and channel selection in sustainable food supply chain based on blockchain technology. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2025.1638313>